

OPINION: On Gurus, Electric Universe Prediction, Bio-electrics, Comets, 5G, and Futurism

A Response to OSHO documentary, COVID-19, the “Invisible Rainbow”, Atlas
C/2019 Y4, and Buckminster Fuller

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ABSTRACT

The pandemic of COVID-19 and subsequent 2020 lockdown has strong conspiratorial elements. How are these related to the Fuller concept of the GRUNCH? What can the actions of religious cults, and the connections of plagues to comets tell us about possible motives of the government? How will this all relate in an EPEMC framework, fully stretching the power of the cosmology to explain disparate subjects through underlying themes and hypotheses. This is an experimental paper in EPEMC which plays upon the predictive power of EPEMC history and anthropology, as well as electro-comets, and can bring some clarity in the “Invisible Rainbow” subject by first eliciting questions which later data can be compared to (in a future paper).

Keywords: COVID-19 - Buckminster Fuller - OSHO - Comet Atlas - Invisible Rainbow - 5G

Convergence of Disparate Studies

It's hard to explain, at first glance, how all of the above are related. But in my mind, they are. First I will readily admit that I got onto the Osho documentary, "Wild, Wild Country" (Netflix), after watching "Tiger King" during the COVID-19 (EVENT 201) *forced* quarantine era. It was even more odd than "Tiger King," in my opinion, due to the fact that it was profoundly important US History which has never been mentioned in any history course or story I have ever heard. Whereas the latter is understandably more recent and private, small time history, the story of the Rajneeshpuram city fiasco¹, scandal, and the fallout surrounding that commune is entirely salient in these *Martial Law* conditions. It, as a documentary, makes it clear that the United States has a disturbing trend of *suspending liberty* for select groups of people, often on arbitrary conditions. Of course, the commune and its leaders were engaged in massive criminal activity, fraud, and multiple shocking felonies (especially as a supposed pacifistic cult). But at the root of it was the cult's radical response to unusual - if not natural and to be expected - anti-liberty responses from Oregonians and government workers.

My response is quite a bit nuanced, however, and in this OpEd I want to focus on the spiritual aspect, with a background on the reflection of the "life out of balance" (Koyaanisqatsi) prevalent in America, the west, etc.² However, I do not feel the discussion can be done justice without a background in discussing both the EPEMC version of the Origins of Religions, and the subsequent momentum and psychological weirdness of humanity since the catastrophes. There is no better way to elucidate this than focus on the approaching comet, Atlas (C2019 Y4).

Finally, in discussing the *response* mankind is having, we cannot help but touch on the New World Order³, Event 201, and the data suggesting prior knowledge of the COVID events, and this brings up (of course) the excellently timed and timeless work of futurist Buckminster Fuller, "GRUNCH of Giants," (1983). I have listened (on audible) to this book due to the suggestion of a mentor (of sorts) and author Robert Kiyosaki, who talked about it in his own book "2nd Chance" on his YouTube channel in which he was making predictions on the market bubble and crash. He claims that his ability to make these predictions has been due to his study of the GR.UN.C.H.⁴ giants, their financial moves, elitist-oligarchical plans for humanity⁵ that are well documented both by their own admissions (such as Bill Gates at TED in 2015⁶) and by documentarian Aaron Russo (deceased), among others⁷. However Robert has quite a lot of money, whereas Aaron was only a friend to the money in Nick Rockefeller. Robert also is friends with President Donald Trump, and co-authored two books with him, and has access to a lot of insiders and financial analysts like James Rickards who have made those predictions of the market reversals.

¹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rajneeshpuram>

² As both a researcher of the Origins of Religions, and of Taoist, Vedic, Buddhist, and early Christian as well as aboriginal conditions, and my practice as a healer, I have plenty of pedigree. Besides, spirituality is not proved through logical debate, but practical effect. The "Nei Yeh" makes clear those who are actually able to avoid Heaven's Disasters and the attacks of animals and people are the sages. They store the Qi in the chest and make the house of it clear. That matches the Egyptian's own theories, and really, just good sense.

³ In March, on LinkedIn, billionaire Ray Dalio openly advocated, in meme form the "Changing World Order" and that is the total sum of what the meme post actually said.

⁴ Gross, Universal, Cash Heist

⁵ Agenda 21, geoengineering, War on Terror, etc.

⁶ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6Af6b_wyiwl "One of these numbers needs to approach zero." ~Bill Gates, implying it was population, with regards to making carbon "approach zero." Of course climate change is natural, solar related, and a fact of human and global history, and not really a long term threat. People have always responded to it by moving inland. That's simply speaking, what will happen over the thousands of years. A more grave threat would be pole flip.

⁷ David Icke, Alex Jones, etc.

Having myself seen the manipulation of the markets in the COVID, with futures trading happening over weekends ahead of market openings, and ahead of forced quarantine orders, my mind wondered, "How much did they know and when?"

Subsequent research has shown that they had quite a few months. How? How could globalists with western interests coordinate with China's CCP (who clearly tried to hide the SARS-cov-2 outbreak⁸ and get rid of evidence, or shift blame from Wuhan bat lab-researcher Jane Qiu^{9 10} and others) when they are potentially fundamental adversaries? The Fed wants dollar dominance and infinite inflation (unless their plan is to shift wealth from the west to China's new, larger economy and burn down the west as they go, which doesn't make much sense¹¹) while the Chinese seek a petro-RMB dominance (openly allying with Russia on their Belt & Road Initiative here). Furthermore, the entire theory discounts the clear "caught with pants down" nature with which the majority of the market - of those not part of the cabal who resigned their companies and went cash in 2018-2019 - were caught and devastated. So what is really going on here? Are there any instances of so many multiple layers of conspiracy being at odds?

Figure 1 - Brightness magnitude tracking Atlas, as compared to the now Memory-Holed "projections" of COVID peak in June^{12 13}; source: <http://www.aerith.net/>¹⁴

I haven't even dug into the grave and irrefutable fact of insider trading by politicians after January briefings, both Republican and Democrat, or the fact of their secret empires and marriage/familial alliances with China and Chinese business/politics, or the obvious political and geo-political nature of the advantage that the Democrats place in garnering power through welfarism, and destroying the economy.

Clearly, there is room for more!

Many are discussing the sudden, but ultimately expected, appearances of 5G towers¹⁵ in the very places of strongest forced quarantine (like New York City). This *could* explain the mysterious support for temporary martial law Trump has allowed, given it is clearly politically disadvantageous of him to give that political leverage (of a fallen economy) to Democrats in an election year. Rather, if he was briefed, following the

⁸ <https://reason.com/2020/03/30/the-world-must-not-mimic-chinas-authoritarian-model-to-fight-covid-19/>

⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CiHWaaJNktQ>

¹⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bpQFCcSI0pU>

¹¹ Only with Agenda 21/2021 would it make sense. But if Agenda 21 is so transparent as that, why try to stop the spread of SARS? Although the isolation has increased the death rate as of this writing, it is expected to ultimately limit it. See: WHO data the author has gathered.

¹² <https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.02.12.20022566v1>

¹³ <https://bit.ly/3c3NPLS>

¹⁴ <http://www.aerith.net/comet/catalog/2019Y4/2019Y4.html>

¹⁵

<https://www.globalresearch.ca/are-5g-biometric-systems-being-covertly-installed-during-lockdown-where-you-live/5707159>

October 18 “Event 201” simulation of Coronavirus¹⁶, and the Wuhan-held Military World Games¹⁷, of the Fed’s intentions and plans (ala inflation to defeat the “evils of deflation”), then he may have had advanced awareness or could have been coerced into a behavior, which in either case would be potentially treasonous. If, however, he was informed of something more intense: the induction of exosomal reaction to the approaching comet Atlas, due to peak in June (which is also when most were projecting this peak back in February and March) 2019 (see Figure 1).

Just what is the evidence that President Trump, Bill Gates (and the NWO¹⁸), the CCP, and others may have had advanced models and knowledge^{19 20} that this virus would spread about, creating exosomes of easy transmission, which would grow apace with the comet’s approach? Given we have to wait to plot the data out, we cannot prove the prediction until July or August, but I can include the data here for review at that time. I already have the WHO daily report data being tracked²¹.

What does this have to do with gurus, one might ask? Nothing on the outside. But everything, if one considers secret government behavior, and more importantly, corrupt and misguided spiritual cults, which *absolutely* have a long history of also being influenced by cosmic events. Not that the Osho events happened recently, but it is interesting that the entire devolution of the modern west is in accord and almost timed with both the self-announcement of the New World Order (vis-a-vis the Trilateral Commission^{22 23 24}) and the degradation of the Earth’s Magnetosphere. This news also follows soon upon the heels of the revelation of not just these COVID conspiracies, but the release of three oddly (and poignantly) classified materials:

1. CIA classified (until 2012) “The Adam and Eve Story” text which describes catastrophe due to crustal displacement and world flipping.²⁵
2. Soviet classified space station footage of odd spinning-wrench flipping, and re-flipping, and re-flipping.²⁶
3. Declassified documents showing the US/USSR cooperation in space electric nuking experiments²⁷, including the help of the oddly-motivated Carl Sagan, who also worked very hard to discredit Immanuel Velikovsky²⁸. Ironically, of course, Velikovsky has been vindicated while now we know Sagan worked on the “nuke the moon”²⁹ plans, and was clearly a government shill the entire time.

Briefly: The Origins of Religions, in terms of How Saturnian era Worship came to define risk mitigation, catastrophe reaction, and Authority

To explain the weird connection between GRUNCH and the fraud Bhagwan/Osho, as well as the overall COVID-19/Event 201 false flag (not hoax!), we need to really go back to the beginning. But rather than repeat

¹⁶ <https://www.bitchute.com/video/D3zF3nbmULJc/>

¹⁷ The 2019 Military World Games, officially known as the 7th CISM Military World Games and commonly known as Wuhan 2019, was held from October 18–27, 2019 in [Wuhan](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2019_Military_World_Games), Hubei, China.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2019_Military_World_Games

¹⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=go8uMp-gUsY>

¹⁹ <https://www.businessinsider.com/biggest-ceo-departures-wework-juul-ebay-warner-bros-metlife-2019-10>

²⁰ <https://www.businessinsider.com/bob-iger-keith-block-ceos-that-stepped-down-in-2020>

²¹ <https://bit.ly/2JFJGSw>

²² http://trilateral.org/download/files/speeches_25_anniversary.pdf

²³ <https://www.issuelab.org/resources/27834/27834.pdf>

²⁴ http://www.thirdworldtraveler.com/New_World_Order/Trilateral_UsurpSovereign.html

²⁵ <https://www.cia.gov/library/readingroom/docs/CIA-RDP79B00752A000300070001-8.pdf>

²⁶ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1VPfZ_XzisU

²⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KcTrOGS3TyE>

²⁸ <https://www.amazon.com/Sagan-Immanuel-Velikovsky-Charles-Ginental/dp/1561840750>

²⁹ <https://nsarchive2.gwu.edu/NSAEBB/NSAEBB479/docs/EBB-Moon02.pdf>

the previous papers on Religions³⁰, Divine Right to Rule³¹, and the giant waste of money in investments towards world-ending weapons³², we'll summarize as follows:

- Prior to the Flare God event during the Tepe Period, the “Atlantean Period” had a purple sky and central pole star, and was characterized as a spring like climate.
- The Younger Dryas was kicked off by an event, this event changed Earth’s orbit creating cold conditions.
- This event presented clusters of impacts from wrecked planetoid material, which electrically exploded.
- It may be when the moon approached, which is our only remaining object with electrical scarring evidence on one side.
- The Tepe period ended with the ejection of Venus and the death of the god, and birth of Kronos
- Later Jupiter/Marduk defeats the Father/Brother (Zeus literally castrates Kronos, removing Mars and Earth and Venus), and the Earth enters a dangerous era.
- Religion goes with mankind under-ground, and hierarchy only continues.
- People are inspired into castes, chiefs, kings, and the origins of divine right to rule.
- These origins of the real Religious Period that came later are less political than motivated by fear of **real** gods, albeit in spherical form.
- As the solar system breaks down, more terrible catastrophes happen leading to “cycles” of catastrophe, and a number of “sun” changes.
- The Earth ends up briefly in the grip of Jupiter.
- Earth leaves Zeus’ control, and flips over, causing another Deluge event, as well as the “Frost giants” etc.
- The moon is captured by Earth permanently, but Mercury/Hermes ends up near the Sun.
- Venus and Mars continue in an orbital electro-tidal lock similar to Earth+Moon and Pluto+Charon, but eventually their nearness to Jupiter causes a thunderbolt to strike Venus and it heads inwards towards the Sun.
- Mankind interprets the Divine Right to Rule, the War of the Gods, the Thunderbolt/Weapon of God as normalcy, and family related.
- Large swaths of mankind engage in plunder economy, now justified not only with war and weapon “might is right” but racism and zealous genocide.
- Mankind enters the Megalithic Period in full worship, exits into the Transition Period in wanton hedonism.
- Mankind witnesses the wrath of Mars at the final last, as it sweeps by the Earth, but then they settle into their final (current) orbits. The year length change requires a SECOND calibration. Great Serpent Mound commemorates the new solstices and equinoxes that are discussed in Chinese record.
- Mankind enters the new Religious Period and creates engineered, bureaucratic forms of religion to create stability and control the masses. They are based on the lost Golden Era, the God, and especially the promise of a messiah. Elsewhere aboriginals retain worship of either Venus/Calf or of a Mars/War god, engaging in animism, spirit worship, ancestor worship, and even human sacrifice and cannibalism.

³⁰ https://www.academia.edu/36753645/On_the_Origins_of_Religions

³¹

https://www.academia.edu/38993303/Caer_Melyn_Camelot_-_Cosmic_Hillfort_of_the_King_The_Yellow_Hill_fort_as_a_Cosmic_Hill_or_mountain_motif_and_symbol_of_a_Kings_authority

³²

https://www.academia.edu/36753646/Investments_in_Ragnarok_Comparisons_and_Conclusions_from_the_study_of_Media_Business_and_Government_investments_in_End_of_the_World_myth_story_and_preparation

- As man completes the Renaissance, religion is distorted into highly abstract concepts, while the Divine Right to Rule justifies brutal acts of colonization. But these provide the material impetus for the Enlightenment which leads to the current Scientific Period.
- At the last, though, religious motifs, patterns of war like behavior and holdout leave an indelible imprint on mankind's economic and social behaviors, which once industrialized quickly spread into mass materialism (due to scientific separatism), and consumerism (due to widespread abundance of energy and proliferation of technology to enable the dominating families to develop societies in unique ways).
- In the background, a lingering doubt of war, obsession with mythic gods, ghosts, and themes of afterlife, death, angels and demons haunts mankind, even as he rapidly abandons chivalry and other traditions which hearken back to those ancient times, when bread and meade was made, and "men were men, and women were women." - and Age of War, wickedness, and widespread poverty and ignorance and bigotry... but always with a clarity of knowing "who we are" (so *they* can be different).

Not everything about this sequence is negative, it is just our tendency to focus there. For example while the Spanish burning of the codices of the Aztecs was itself an evil act, the fact remains that the Spanish conquered *because* a) they had technology and more importantly b) they had the help of locals who were sick of the brutal heart sacrifice and slavery of the Mexica, who were oppressing them. Moreover, the spread of the pox began from Chinese delegations, not Spanish, and then later the French who care not who they gave the pox to, so long as trade continued. The Spanish committed many atrocities, not the least of which was rape, arson, murder, and theft. But they most definitely ended the Aztec supremacy and wanton human sacrifice of hundreds of thousands of people, mostly virgin women and young men, and one of the least publicized genocides of imperial histories.

There were many other great things accomplished by organized religions, and by organized empires. Just as there are, now, in the technocracy and oligarchy of the modern world, many excellent advancements (like literacy, food, "clean" water, clothing, leisure time), we see a constant thread of human achievement and the spirit of overcoming. A stoic form of hope, or an optimistic chain of unbridled enthusiasm.

But, there is also a dark side to this. An unstated fact, or series of facts, which remain curiously unchallenged - even in the privacy of homes - even in the face of horrific facts of tyranny, oppression, and destitution we are *now* capable of, **even in the midst of massive economic prosperity, access, and dream-like freedom over the material world.** Such dreams can, and have, rapidly created or turned to nightmares, due to - on the one hand - our childlike innocence or naivety about the consequences of the forces we play with, and the nature of our reality (matrix bedamned). On the other hand, there is the sheer existence and fact of evil: of hidden malice, both human and likely systemic, or even supra-conscious (or other conscious), and of outright criminal evil, betrayal, fraud, destruction, and of course, endless war.

It is with *this* background that we can thence begin to understand the bizarre world we have come to occupy, and the weird, almost dystopian connection of fraudulent cult leaders (and the fakeness and fake news surrounding them, and their true oppression history which certifies for them the uniqueness of their not-so-new religious actions), with factual occult-obsessed pedophile elites engaged in sex, human, organ, and maybe even "human meat" trafficking, who probably have a financial grip upon the planet for their own greedy selfish power, but may in fact be mere pawns for an outside force. Regardless, this cabal of globalist elites who are in competition with each other benefit from our confusion and discord, and grow apace. They now no longer care to announce themselves, their intentions, and have no fear of repression or repercussion because they do not believe in the Creator God, for he is "dead" and they do not fear the religious and political authorities, or their police dogs, because **they own them.**

The sooner people wake up to this, the quicker they can analyze it and understand it. Alas, it is not such an easy puzzle to understand: "what's this evil I detect around me?" The human mind is designed to live in the forest (of ignorance mostly), not in the [plain] light of Truth. It runs on cognitive bias, pattern recognition

and discrimination, on fear and belief in lack, and at the genetic level: self-domestication. The body produces a Substance P (for pain), but the mind a Substance F, for fear. Think about this issue deeply, and realize the trap the most elite of powers can utilize here! It is mere child's play for someone with billions of dollars, working with others with billions, who together control trillions of dollars, to enact. It isn't even remotely a difficulty. It is merely a matter of cohesion and will to act. Since the end of World War II, they have, in fact, had all the means, motive, and opportunity to do so, and with barely any opposition at all from those bereft of access and resources, knowledge and focus, nor from those invested in the system's protection, such as police, military, or regular voters besotted with material wealth and a wine based on pacifistic ignorance and naive religious fear of accumulation of wealth.

Origins of the GRUNCH Giants and their Metaphoric Power Come to Modern Reality

"There were giants in the earth in those days." ~Genesis

What are these giants that Mr. Fuller speaks of? They are not likely linear descendents of Annunaki/Nephilim (but they might be) but they are descendents of the ancient line of *haves*. Those who, from the end of the era of equanimity began the long descent into positional battle of political leadership, religious control, and fiscal domination, have kept their might lofty, and reduced the weakest of people to puppets, slaves, victims, thralls, lackeys, and in many ways chattel.

They were tribal elders, and shaman, who retained knowledge, priests and monks who presided over the access, rabbi and bishops who hid it in secret, kings and dukes who lorded with it, merchants and scientists who shaped the world with it, philosophers and lawyers lied about it, and farmers and traders, explorers and sailors searched for it, worked for it, and ultimately have never found it.

The metaphor of *giants* of knowledge, power, and access - of heroes - became, in effect, through the embodiment and creation of corporations, real giants which can and do dominate the world through currency. Current is one of two parts of power, the other being *potential* or [in]tension. Potential is obvious but who would have thought that the Magna Carta would unleash the power of the holy leaders which was bound up, and put it into the hands of the secular (and maybe amoral) group of oligarchs whose families have come down through the ages of nobility into the current ranks of billionaires and multi-millionaires? Currency was not really a strong idea (and finance basically had no concept) in the Dark Ages. But in the age of colonialism, the royal families, especially of Spain and England, supplied *guarantees* of endless currency and security of investment to exploring merchants. They *knew* of the Americas and also desired the trade routes, and they allowed these explorers to battle for lands already in others possession, because ultimately their power was able to be leant and so extended, to these conquistadors, fur traders, and explorers. They created new giants who laid the groundwork for corporate giants, who re-invested (or 200 years) back into the scientific and technological progress, that led **directly** to the final release of the first secrets of electromagnetic, atomic, chemical, and capitalistic power.

The industrial mogul was born by *using* these beautiful fools (like Tesla), and harnessing their gifts, and the forces of the Universe to propel them beyond mere giant status to *titanic*. JP Morgan, Westinghouse, Chase, Vanderbilt, Rockefeller... these are the names of *gods* in capitalism, finance, and industry. They were followed by and surrounded by other giants. They invented things, or controlled the invention and design of things and influenced things done, such as the invention of the Federal Reserve (which still took decades to enact) at Jekyll Island.

They were the original New World Order and though they weren't original royalty, they were the new Royals. They were joined by thousands of wannabes and hangers on, as well as dozens of compatriots (in finance) and competitors, and they existed in a league of their own. No one and nothing could compare. Rather than be afraid of Senators, you for the first time could not just influence one to be bought as usual, but buy a politician position. You could literally bankroll their campaign and destroy the hopes of a regular, better knowing constituent who would be more liked but unable to *access* the people and media most needed to *get your name out there*.

For the first time mankind could *afford* to systematically buy out, or continually steal without much repercussions, the world of finance and other economies. Usually in history the giants *took* the money and resources by force. But this isn't strictly necessary in the industrialized world. Instead, it can just be taken, like an adult can take a toy from a child by merely lifting it over their heads. Whereas before they needed swords, now they have the pen and then digital pen! The digital pen must be 10,000 times stronger than a sword, in the end.

What has he done with it? Largely good things, in terms of education, employment, and raising standards of living. Of course the latter *only* happens because people *buy* things that improve their lives. Otherwise there is no evidence that the same energy would be invested in for mere philanthropy. Rather isn't it most unusual, though, that the education provided to this day has no bearing on or revelation of the secrets of finance and business that these men had inherited and perfected, and taught to other corporate executives and moguls? As for employment, like any trade there is no inherent virtue (or shame) in a trade. So the morality of the employment would depend really upon the particular situation.

It has also done a countless number of immoral, illegal, unethical, and evil things which have often undone the good things mentioned, or more likely: marred them. So the issue remains to ask, what is the significance of this behavior and power inherited of *direct currency*. The true extent of this power flow moves in an ever increasing influence, as well. As time grows, it also accelerates and expands its power ..

Let us go back, though, before investing into the modern Grunch power, to discussing the power of *religious authorities*. In the United States, the Constitution and particularly the Bill of Rights which are designed to imply perfect freedom and right to religious liberty throughout the territories of the country. However, in practice there is a difference of hierarchy and degree of freedom. Naturally, up until recently Christianity was the dominant religious force, outside of Authority and the belief in authority's sovereignty. Now it is multiple forces, all vying for that control.

Within that context, the rise of the New Age, of revivalist style cults, and of fundamentalists or even terrorists is not so shocking. Their desire to utilize the guarantees of the idealistic Bill of Rights almost makes sense. But the actual outcome cannot help but be influenced by humanity's past, and the actions of Grunch style world domination.

Take the Bhagwan as the prime example. He was a man who was highly educated, thoughtful, and ambitious. In the end, however, he was just another hippy fooling fraud who liked owning excessive amounts of Rolls Royces, expensive watches, doing drugs, and exploiting the labor of others while trying to avoid culpability and risk. He was not a spiritual leader, he was the antithesis. But, it did not stop people from having some legitimate spiritual benefits. Certainly the commune was, at first, an incredibly organized but passionate and inspiring bit of human social behavior. They built buildings, farms, electrical and water grids, a dam, and more. It was an experiment never done before: a capitalist led hippy commune and haven.

It has also basically not been repeated. The location was poorly chosen, and the execution flawed, but the most primary reason is that the U Government killed Rajneehpuram, as did the Oregonians, in a display of power and dominance. It found legitimate violations and criminal, even fascist and homicidal behavior, and this lead to the execution of judicial power upon the leadership. It was a strong deterrent, and obviously the same methods of funding the situation would not be easily repeated or reinstated. Only established Grunch style bonafide (or nearly so) religions would be capable! Or crazy ones which the NWO did not mind because they

were anti-Christian. As for Osho he was defeated by the underlings of Grunch who act in many ways like gatekeepers to the power/revenue source. The price of his *dare* - or his secretary's - was to be swatted down, and removed further from central power.

This is a man who was a rock star everywhere he went... fully capable of ripping off people to promise them something they would ultimately not get. He was silent for years, and later regretted the Bhagwan identity and Rajneeshism, and destroyed all of it to change his legacy. But despite having thousands of followers, he was but an insignificant ant compared to the power of the super elite, and their Grunch masterpiece of machined, raw power.

In short: he was crushed, and rightfully so, given he had condoned in one way or another the criminal behavior of his secretary. That isn't the subject of this paper, however. Rather, the point is that she was enabled to act as he would, and he would act fraudulently. So that's what he was and she was, and they both served their time.

However, those who could violate the commune's rights, or condone a fire bombing of property, and flip the world over, effectively, are those who stand the most to gain from Grunch by stopping him. Ironic: he chose the Grunch path over the spiritual word and he paid for that, with his money, and his time, and retirement.

To be plain he had nothing to be ashamed about in terms of making money, or spending it, so long as safety is guarded, and opportunities shared, etc. However, we also do not have such a condition. Which makes what I am about to say the most salient fact - and frightening: Grunch can choose to act as tyrant or protector, and this is from many points of view totally arbitrary. It is **not** arbitrary however, when it involves flattening a religious man of fame, wealth, and ability (even if criminal). It is, in fact, that the predictable outcome is if that opposing religious man is a threat to Grunch. If they join in, do they kowtow or harbor their own version? It will be case by case. Somehow, though, decisions are made and executed despite it being pretty easy to justify using Grunch methods. It doesn't really matter if the middle level Grunch seeker has a desire to be a threat, or even spread that hatred. Instead, it matters if the kowtow cedes real, tangible position in the Grunch game and arena. Those who don't give up, gain more ground. Those who give up will find themselves always behind the Grunch machine. That especially includes those that half play the game, and through religious methods or other "unnatural" means (from the perspective of the Grunch Giants). Think of the number of ruined careers and true "Hollywood stories" or conspiracies that basically involve either religion, cults, etc. coming down on even powerful, famous, or connected people. Scientology is replete, in its short career, with these stories.

Who is a giant if not the celebrity? Somebody with real access and power. Like the famous horse head bed scene in Godfather shows, your kind of famous, showy power is fine for who you are... but those with connections to the Grunch, even or especially its criminal side, and with ancient knowledge, will of course **crush** upstarts.

In other words, Osho/Bhagwan and his secretary dared to dream outside their station in that great world of religion and cults, and were then consequently *stepped on*. They fought a strong fight, but their human frailties got in the way as she committed so many crimes, and he tried to flee, only to be caught and paraded like a dog before deportation. So it was that they fell apart from each other, and failed to get enough power to make their reality a total and permanent dream. They were *shattered by the Hammer* (a weapon of the War God.) The System literally denied them rights to vote, because it recognized the violation of the spirit of the voting and government policies, from the perspective of white, western American democracy. They tried to game the System, and were dutifully crushed. It happens to also be true that they were criminals, involved in clawing their way up the ladder in a darker path. This only engaged the righteous power of the government and its lawyers, etc. If Osho hadn't fled by plane, many people would have died as the government felt the need to crush the cult.

And why wouldn't they be? Why is it that we pretend this isn't the way things really are? It is the lie that things are based in love alone. It's a simple fact of life that they aren't based in love alone. It may or may not be a sick reality. But it is reality, nevertheless.

They reflected each other! And both have their origins in *that ancient time*.

The 5G Nightmare? Or is it that another mechanism has been hidden?

It is a widespread assumption of altstream people, that **because the Universe is electromagnetic**, that therefore the right alternate explanation to seek for the plannedemic (Event 201) is 5G. There is a correlation of massive 5G coverage in New York City and huge COVID outbreak. But I am not aware, at this time, of equal worldwide data released. Besides there are the facts we already know about the SARS research of Jane Qiu et al. and the Chinese coverup. It seems *extremely unlikely* that there is no virus at all.

Could 5G be used to send out an activation signal which then causes a previously caught virus to increase in power? Sure. But it sounds more like science fiction than bioelectricity in action.

However, in *exosomal theory*, it is far more possible that the virus was spread, probably through the mail, throughout China and then the world, and then people's bodies produced antibodies and released exosomes. Then the comet approaching induced the carrier code into action and more intense, life-threatening activity.

It is also simply possible that the 5G weakens the body and *some people* become more susceptible to pathogens generally. It will take a lot of time to discern the actual mechanism of spread, contraction, activation, and even how it acts within the body. There's some evidence that it does not really cause ARDS and pneumonia, like flu³³ so it is safe to say we don't really know much about this 'virus' at all. Even its size is under dispute, and if its RNA is exosomal rather than viral, it totally changes the complexity and context of this plague.

So assuming it is not a 5G activation, how would the virus or exosome potentially be connected ahead of time to the comet? It may, in fact be true, that how fast viruses have spread through human populations has drastically increased because of the global mailing system and exchange of cash. If that's true, then it's possible the elite had this spread about for months ahead of time, in anticipation of the spread of a plague induced by the comet.

What other plagues, if any, have been associated with comets?

- ★ 10 plagues of Egypt (Exodus era) - Comet Venus (the calf)
- ★ 165 AD - worldwide plague of 15 years - comet recorded by China³⁴
- ★ 535/565AD - Plague in Britain and beyond³⁵ and worldwide cooling³⁶ - comet recorded by China³⁷
- ★ 1918 flu - comet Haley passed in 1910 (so this is a panspermia theory, rather than induction)³⁸
- ★ 2007+ - H1N1 and come Enke, again a panspermia theory³⁹

³³ A lot of cognitive bias comes into comparing this to influenza, not the least of which is calling COVID-19 "kung flu," a hilarious name, but not accurate.

³⁴ https://astronomy.wikia.org/wiki/Comet_appearances_in_China

³⁵ <https://www.pastmedicalhistory.co.uk/plagues-comets-and-volcanoes/>

³⁶ https://www.vice.com/en_us/article/4x3yeg/a-comet-tried-to-kill-earth-with-the-black-death

³⁷ <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/full/1972MmRAS..76...27K>

³⁸ <http://journalofcosmology.com/Panspermia10.html>

³⁹ "13. Conclusions

Correlation is not causation and thus no firm conclusions can be drawn, despite the wealth of evidence suggesting a link between comets and diseases from space. Nevertheless, comets are an ideal vehicle for sustaining and transporting a variety of microbes, including viruses, from planet to planet and even from solar system to solar system. In consequence, when these organisms are deposited on a world already thriving with life, genes may be exchanged, the evolution of new

So it isn't a trivial list, but it isn't exhaustive, either. It is compelling, but it clearly needs more research. As for a mechanism which is potentially involved it would be a 3 part process:

1. Lab created or fostered (from study and breeding) of SARS loses virus or participates with NWO to engineer a release. Lab tech disappears so no way to know. Possibly it was released in the "wet market"
2. It spreads throughout the most integrated with China portions of the world. People's bodies produce exosomes.
3. The comet, as it approaches, has a certain signal, and it was known to be mimetic with the virus, and this activates in people with weakened immune systems.

The best evidence for this spread as a population control is the behavior of world elite Grunch Giants, such as Bill Gates, to leave their companies in peak waves in October and January, hoard their cash⁴⁰, participate in a simulation, create the COVID Act Now group⁴¹, and spread fear via mainstream media.

The best evidence that this is more about control, a currency and trade war, is the same basic actions but instead the spread of State control, fear based media, and of course, the hidden motives becoming semi-hidden actions in policy during a lockdown.

The best evidence for a China led weaponization /assassin's mace being used against the west, particularly America, aided with a Deep State of marxist and socialist sympathizers, who harbor spies⁴² and traitors within the United States and Europe, is the fact that China covered up the virus⁴³, spread it wantonly, promoted "hug a Chinese" days in Italy⁴⁴, clearly swayed and bullied the World Health Organization⁴⁵, and of course, appears poised to benefit the most from the US inflation + forced shutdown⁴⁶. Where did the Covid Act Now models come from which were used in January to frighten governors and Congress into action⁴⁷? Why did the NBA, of all organizations shut down so quickly⁴⁸? After all, the NBA is well known and heavily tied to China⁴⁹. After previous criticisms in Hong Kong surface, it was the NBA and its giant stars, like Lebron James which took to the liberal social media to defend China's tyrannical behaviors⁵⁰, and in effect encourage people to overlook their organ harvesting programmes and concentration camps for Muslims and Falun Gong, etc. Also even after the entire event, China has somehow managed to join the UN Human Rights and Health boards⁵¹.

species may ensue, or conversely contagion may be unleashed, and disease, death, and plague may spread throughout the land." *ibid*.

⁴⁰ <https://www.cnbc.com/2019/11/04/warren-buffett-has-128-billion-in-cash-to-burn.html> (note the date)

⁴¹ <https://www.phii.org/blog/podcast-leo-nissola-covid-act-now>

⁴² <https://sanfrancisco.cbslocal.com/2018/08/01/details-chinese-spy-dianne-feinstein-san-francisco/>

⁴³ <https://www.axios.com/china-coronavirus-cover-up-wuhan-pandemic-fa894bb8-998d-494b-8e7a-e834f86d2ea9.html>

⁴⁴ <https://texags.com/forums/16/topics/3101771>

⁴⁵ <https://www.cfr.org/blog/who-and-china-dereliction-duty>

⁴⁶

<https://www.marketwatch.com/story/china-will-emerge-from-the-coronavirus-crisis-stronger-than-the-us-experts-warn-2020-03-24>

⁴⁷ <https://thefederalist.com/2020/03/25/inaccurate-virus-models-are-panicking-officials-into-ill-advised-lockdowns/>

⁴⁸

<https://www.usatoday.com/story/sports/nba/2020/03/12/nba-shut-down-least-month-says-commissioner-adam-silver/5038940002/> (almost 2 weeks before the rest of the economy)

⁴⁹ <https://www.usatoday.com/story/sports/nba/2019/10/07/nbas-ties-with-china-worth-billions-now-under-strain/40278283/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.nbcnews.com/think/opinion/what-did-lebron-james-say-about-china-nearly-everyone-else-ncna1069131>

⁵¹ <https://unwatch.org/china-joins-u-n-human-rights-panel-will-help-pick-experts-on-free-speech-health-arbitrary-detention/>

But it is entirely possible that this is a *Black Swan* event that the NWO elite take advantage of, by positioning themselves first... like a volleyball player jumps to spike the ball and eventually finds the right moment, and now that the comet Atlas provides a mechanism, BOOM!

Grunchy Answers...

Actually, it doesn't matter which of the above are true, because the reality of the Gross Universal Cash Heist is what remains true regardless. Included below are charts of the markets which show the mysterious moves, blamed on a virus *before* the shutdown and the whole world was aware of it, and the even more inexplicable reversal of the bear market, given the economy is shut down...

Figure 2 (left): Sharp end to the bear market, for 3 weeks straight; Figure 3 (right): down channel

Figure 4: the historic Bull Run, in the context of the inflation balloon of cheap cash
 Harvesting the Bull Run would be a wise action by any trader, anytime, and then “buy the bottom”
 But how would the elites know where the bottom is? How were they declaring we had peak virus
 movement a day before the world peak was being reached? And certainly before the US peak⁵² has yet been
 reached in new infections and deaths!

- April 5th/6th: market claims peak is reached⁵³; correlates with an April 6 market open spike
- April 7: first deceleration of US new infections reported in WHO daily reports.
- April 9: Us New Deaths spike further, according to the highly flawed WHO data.

⁵² <https://www.cnbc.com/2020/04/04/coronavirus-live-updates-us-cases-continue-to-rise-faster-than-other-countries.html>

⁵³ <https://www.businessinsider.com/coronavirus-investing-strategy-top-market-economy-metrics-14-experts-outlook-2020-4>

US new Infx vs.

Figure 5 - First drop in US new infections on April 7

US New deaths vs.

Figure 6 - Massive spike April 9

Market Summary > Dow Jones Industrial Average

INDEXDJX: .DJI

+ Follow

23,719.37 +285.80 (1.22%) ↑

Apr 9, 5:15 PM EDT · Disclaimer

Figure 7 - Unexplained Bear Reversal April 6th, economy still shut down and airplane refunds increasing

So are Electronics using the “Invisible Rainbow” the enemy or what?

It is a fact that harnessing the electric force, even if wrongly done (instead of pulling or using telluric, we *push* it and this may be the issue, from a physics and philosophical perspective), has in fact led to advancement of human civilization and improvement in our daily conditions. It has also led to drastic world-altering issues of health, erosion, pollution, and war. It might very well be that, if one does not allow Dao to manifest itself, and use low energy techniques to harness the natural flow of energy in nature (such as waterfall turbines), then we will be destined via some kind of Universal Karma to suffer from our presumptuousness. But we cannot, and let's be honest, will not go back in time. The Egyptians were wiser than us, they stored the Truth in stone, a medium which has lasted the test of time, and in image, a media form we can now use to seek Truth. But when they engineered their Earth based resonator power plant, it did not stop their society from disappearing, ultimately. They did not master themselves, in all sectors of society, even with all their engineers and craftsmen, and they had incredibly powerful Grunch Giants called pharaohs. We are still obsessed with them.

I have said this before, and I will say it again, “People are the problem and people will be the solution; technology is a problem, it will also give us a solution.” Therefore I do not advocate fear of the electromagnetic force, but instead the use of, and reasonably common release and treatment through acupuncture and other techniques of the excess charges that get lodged in the body through the signals sent by the electronic culture, radar, radio, TV, cell phone, HAARP, 5G, etc. It is likely only going to spread and multiply, exponentially even

(with the Internet of Things) and so become a problem of health and human culture. Culture degradation, and culture wars, will only accelerate from here on out as globalism has provided the impetus and means for a form of dangerous, toxic entanglement that deprives not just the aboriginal but even the civilized and relatively well armed and informed person of the upper middle class, of the ability to actually punish or give retribution, or even just prevent incursions into one's life from the Grunch Giants.

If this person, male or female, considers what "should be done" is it to refuse to use the tools of technological leverage and weaponry? Rather, he/she should use it, and dutifully, in order to strike fear *back* into the hearts of those that govern, to remind them that they govern at the behest and permission of the People, and not of themselves.

Is Grunch the controversial solution?

The Grunch giants are a fierce and fearsome enemy of the common man, spiritualist, or whoever. But, they also have discovered some interesting facets or truths of the Universe by inheriting the techniques of Grunch from the giants of the past, who inherited the divine right to rule from tribal elders worldwide, who learned it, with people, from the behaviors of the "gods" (planets and stars). Also, they have learned to harness the superstitious nature of people's ignorance, and to harness the leveraged advancement of technology. So how is it that we can set aside those powerful advancements, and what right would we have anyhow to pretend it will go away merely from wishful thinking?

Instead, it requires getting incredibly more sophisticated, prepared, and **realistic** about the effects of these Giants (and their origins of powers) in our lives. In the first place you will basically never meet a common person who isn't engaged in some kind of *ism*, cult or revolution who doesn't question the Police State, and the *forced*, unnatural order created by the giants and their lackeys, but populated and supported by everyday common people. That's a massive problem. Because any effort done without first a question of assumptions and apriori knowledge, is like as not to be the road paved to Hell with "good intentions." It isn't that criminals are scarce, or "not a problem" so much as the fact that the government (as shown in the 20th century without a doubt) constitutes the majority of homicidal and genocidal megalomania. That includes all proto-governments, NGOs, the NWO, finance, etc.

So how can one utilize the 'black magic' of the Grunch in control? It must be finance, and politics, and it must be a solution that common people are willing to be personally involved in, instead of foisting the solution finding upon completely disparate groups and people, most of which are probably just as disenfranchised, if not *more* than you are.

Save the solutions of violence and force for the absolutely necessary period, which almost surely comes if history holds true lessons. Instead, activate a willingness to fight the Grunch, but not by deceiving it (that's impossible, it **is** deception, incarnate), but by using its own tools and ladders within it. And with courage, take no quarter, and activate the sharpest and most capable, transformational version of yourself. In my case, it means learning mergers & acquisitions. What will it mean to you, I do not know. But there are a lot of potential abilities latent within every person, and I am sure that a solution to your freedom, and unlocked ability will lie within your current life. But, in my opinion, you should remain wary of the precarious nature of the Grunch system now, and its massive potential for violence and action against regular people.

However you deal with the emerging truths of the plasma-electromagnetic Universe, and of the evidence and knowledge of the huge conspiracy and false flag against us, be sure that you do not lose yourself, to either madness or succumbing to the lies of a **vested system**.

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